

AN ANALYSIS OF CAPM MODEL FOR PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MARKET INDIA WITH REFERENCE TO BANKING, IT, AUTOMOBILE SECTOR COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

Indian stock market has seen phenomenal and incredible growth in recent times. This is largely due to increased income level, change in investor's behavior. The impact of annual performance on the price movement of the shares of the companies continues to be an important research question in finance. A study of the stock market with respect to factors affecting the supply and demand of stocks helps to understand the intrinsic value of shares and to know whether the Shares are undervalued or overvalued. The stock market indicators would help the investor to Identify major market turning points. The objective of this paper to examine whether different sector companies has been able to generate value for its shareholders and to compute the performance of companies by applying new corporate performance measure EVA as per CAPM model of selected stocks of Banking, IT, Automobile sector companies. This study is purely based on data provided on stocks listed in Indian Stock market. For the purpose of analysis, techniques used as Average/Mean, Standard Deviation, Co Efficient of Variance, Return and Beta.

Keywords: CAPM, EVA, Standard Deviation, Co Efficient of Variance, Return and Beta.

INTRODUCTION

Stock Market is one of the most vibrant sectors in the financial system, marking an important contribution to economic development. Liberalization creates important impact on performance of stock market in India. Besides enabling mobilizing resources for investment, directly from the investors, providing liquidity for the investors and monitoring and disciplining company managements are the principal functions of the stock markets. The main attraction of the stock markets is that they provide for entrepreneurs and governments a means of mobilizing resources directly from the investors, and to the investors they offer liquidity. It has also been suggested that liquid markets improve the allocation of resources and enhance prospects of long term economic growth. Further Stock Market is a place where buyers and sellers of securities can enter into transactions to purchase and sell shares, bonds, debentures etc. In other words Stock Market is a platform for trading various securities and derivatives. Further, it performs an important role of enabling corporate, entrepreneurs to raise resources for their companies and business ventures through public issues. Today long term investors are interested to invest in the Stock market rather than invest anywhere

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Calum G Turvey, Linda Lake, Erna van Duren, David Sparling (2000) "The relationship between economic value added and the stock market performance of agribusiness firms" In the present paper

Autors has been tried to investigate the relationship between economic value added (EVA) and the stock market performance of 17 publicly traded companies in the Canadian food processing sector. Researcher has been using 1996 annual reports to compute EVA, and daily stock prices for 1994 through 1998; they attempt to correlate EVA with a variety of measures including accounting return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), share price, the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) returns and risk, and others. Research paper concludes that little support for the speculation that high-EVA firms lead to higher shareholder value. **Taylor, Lynda; Woods, Margaret; Cheng Ge Fang, Gloria**, (2014) “How using EVA Target Costing can Align the Interests of your Shareholders and Customers” In the present study researcher has been attempt to discover economic value added (EVA) target costing, arguing that strategic management accounting and value-based management strategies can be combined to balance the low-cost demands of customers with the investment interests of shareholders as of 2014. **Mohammad Norouzi & Mahmoud Samadi**,(2013), “The Study of Relationship Between Refined Economic Value Added (Reva) and Different Criteria of the Risk Adjusted Return” The present research conducted to study the information content of the refined economic value added and the different criteria of the risk adjusted return (RVAR,RVOL, α) during the years between 2007 and 2011 for 200 companies accepted in Tehran Stock Exchange. Present study concluded that there is a positive relationship between the refined economic value added and the total risk adjusted return but regarding the relationship between refined economic value added and the systematic risk adjusted return, on the contrary to acceptance of a negative relationship between them, the relationship between them was assessed to be weak. Finally the refined economic value added has had a positive relationship with the excess return. **Nikhil Chandra Shil**,(2009), “Performance Measures: An Application of Economic Value Added”, In this paper, efforts have been made to explain theoretical foundation of EVA with its origin, definition, different adjustments, scopes etc. Researcher also define theoretical step – by- step process & methodology which was used for the study. Researcher concluded that EVA should be used with other to take decisions more effectively. Companies may go for simulations over past several years’ performance to find out the areas where EVA as a managerial tool is stronger over

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The value creation by Indian corporate companies are needed to proper investments in capital market and EVA is as better parameter to study the real value of the corporate in Indian concerned. Furthermore In the present scenario investors are hesitant to invest in risky assets. There has always been a fear of burning hands of oneself in this volatile stock market. To understand the significant relationship between risk and return of securities, and examine the implication of Capital Asset Pricing Model in the Indian stock market in determining the required rate of return of risky securities researcher has chosen this topic.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To examine whether different sector companies has been able to generate value for its shareholders.
- 2) To compute the performance of companies by applying new corporate performance measure EVA as per CAPM model.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H0: There is no significance difference in the performance of Companies during the study period.

H0: There is no significance difference in the value creation ability of companies during the study period.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Scope of the study has Economic Value Added and applicability of CAPM in Indian stock market. For that purpose researcher has calculate EVA as per CAPM approach.

STATISTICAL TOOLS

1. Average/Mean ,Standard Deviation, Co Efficient of Variance, Return.
2. Beta

TECHNIQUES

- a. Economic Value Added: It is one of the modern techniques for performance measurement of corporate unit. EVA focuses on clear surplus in contradiction to the traditionally used profit available to the shareholder.

EVA = ADJUSTED NET PROFIT – WACC X Capital Employed.

Where WACC = weighted average cost of capital WACC = weight to $K_e \times K_e +$
weight to $K_d \times K_d$

- b. Capital Asset Pricing Model is one of the most important techniques to evaluate the corporate sector unit. CAPM has been used to calculate cost of equity capital by applying following formula:

$$R_j = R_f + \beta_j \times (R_m - R_f)$$

Where R_j = the expected rate of return on security j

- c. ANOVA: Analysis of variance (abbreviated as ANOVA) is an extremely useful technique concerning researches in the field of economics, business/ industry and in researches of several other disciplines. When researches are conducted any field of knowledge it has a variability in the set of data.

DATA COLLECTION

This study is based on secondary data. The data has been collected from published annual report of selected companies. The population of the study consists of three corporate sectors which are listed in BSE with their 3 companies.

EVA OF BSE –COMPANIES DURING THE STUDY PERIOD (2012 TO 2016)

Rs. in Cr.

	Companies		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	Mean
	Sector/Industry	Company Name						
Banking		SBI Ltd	-32643.5	-46358	-54462	-43670	-60834	-47594
		HDFC Ltd	61.9	211.6	313.0	580.0	1242.7	481.8
		ICICI Bank Ltd	-29940	-29647	-22688	-21966	-25090	-25866
Information Technology		Infosys	2930.9	3793.1	3268.5	3545.3	4287.8	3565.1
		Wipro	1552.8	1177.0	2663.8	2177.2	1243.8	1762.9
		TCS	3258.2	3000.7	3703.9	5118.4	7842.0	4584.6
Automotive		Tata Motors Ltd	416.2	-1886.1	-1786.1	-2504.2	-2551.4	-1662.3
		Maruti Suzuki	677.4	-33.8	1049.2	585.3	-298.7	395.9
		Bajaj Auto	678.3	542.1	1466.2	2196.5	2370.0	1450.6

Above mention table no.1 shows EVA of BSE – 30 companies during the study period. EVA is the modern performance evaluation tool. It was (-1718.9) cr. Average EVA during the study period. With 7844.4 cr. Average EVA ONGC Ltd. got first position among BSE – 30 companies during the study period. From the above table it was found that TCS Ltd., Infosys Ltd., Coal India Ltd. and ITC Ltd. getting 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th rank respectively during the study period. While SBI Ltd. having last position with (- 47593.5) cr. EVA during the study period. Furthermore it was also analyze that 10 companies destroy their shareholder’s value during the study period. Researcher has also found that banking sector having the performance among 16 sectors of BSE – 30 during the study period.

TWO WAY ANOVA FOR EVA OF 3SECTORS COMPANIES

Source of Variation	SS	D.F.	M.S.	F	Fcrit
SS between Rows	165164	8	521944938	24.78	1.56
SS between Columns	1112	4	5741710.1	1.02	2.45
Error	183662368	32	5625380.1		
Total	183828644	45			

Result of two way ANOVA table Computed value of F between row = 24.78 Critical value of F at 5% significance level between row = 1.56 Result = H1 Accepted Computed value of F between column = 1.02 Critical value of F at 5% significance level between column = 2.45 Result = H0 Accepted Above mention Table No. 5.41 disclose two – way ANOVA for EVA of BSE – 30 companies during the study period. Since computed value of F between rows (24.78) is higher than critical/ table value (1.56), null hypothesis has been rejected and alternative hypothesis has been accepted. It shows that there is significant difference in the value creation ability of 3 different sectors companies during the study period. Since computed value of F between columns 1.02 is lower than critical value 2.45, null hypothesis has been accepted. It shows that there is no significant difference in the EVA during the study period. Whatever difference are there it is due to chance.

OVER/UNDERVALUATION OF 3 DIFFERENT SECTORS COMPANIES DURING THE STUDY PERIOD (2012 TO 2016)

Sl No.	Years	Company	Expected Return	Actual Return	Differences	Beta	Undervalued/Overvalued
	2012	SBI Ltd.	0.134	Na	-0.134	Na	Na
	2013		0.113	0.002	0.111	1.04	overvalued
	2014		0.137	-0.001	-0.138	1.05	overvalued
	2015		0.136	0.003	0.133	1.08	overvalued
	2016		0.140	0.001	0.139	1.16	overvalued
	2012	HDFC ltd	0.114	Na	-0.114	Na	Na
	2013		0.103	0.002	0.101	1.23	overvalued
	2014		0.133	-1.002	-0.135	1.03	overvalued
	2015		0.134	0.000	0.134	1.11	overvalued
	2016		0.120	0.021	0.099	0.97	overvalued
	2012	ICICI Ltd	0.101	Na	-0.101	Na	Na
	2013		0.103	0.002	0.101	1.23	overvalued
	2014		0.133	-0.002	-0.135	1.03	overvalued
	2015		0.134	0.000	0.134	1.11	overvalued
	2016		0.120	0.021	0.099	0.97	overvalued
	2012	Infosys	0.111	Na	-0.111	Na	Na
	2013		0.101	0.001	0.1	1.13	overvalued
	2014		0.131	-0.012	-0.143	1.01	overvalued
	2015		0.124	0.011	0.113	1.10	overvalued
	2016		0.121	0.023	0.098	0.37	overvalued

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	2012	Wipro	0.101	Na	-0.101	Na	Na
	2013		0.113	0.012	0.101	1.10	overvalued
	2014		0.121	0.111	0.01	1.03	overvalued
	2015		0.120	0.113	0.007	1.02	overvalued
	2016		0.117	0.107	0.01	0.41	overvalued
	2012	TCS	0.104	Na	-0.104	Na	Na
	2013		0.103	0.002	0.101	1.10	overvalued
	2014		0.121	0.111	0.01	1.03	overvalued
	2015		0.131	0.113	0.018	1.02	overvalued
	2016		0.117	0.109	0.008	0.41	overvalued
	2012	Tata Motors	0.103	Na	-0.103	Na	Na
	2013		0.113	0.012	0.101	1.10	overvalued
	2014		0.121	0.111	0.01	1.03	overvalued
	2015		0.120	0.113		1.02	overvalued
	2016		0.127	0.107		0.41	overvalued
	2012	Maruti Suzuki	0.111	Na	-0.111	Na	Na
	2013		0.013	0.001	0.012	1.10	overvalued
	2014		0.121	0.005	0.116	1.03	overvalued
	2015		0.310	0.110	0.2	1.02	overvalued
	2016		0.117	0.112	0.005	0.41	overvalued
	2012	Bajaj Auto	0.110	Na	-0.110	Na	Na
	2013		0.103	0.005	0.098	1.10	overvalued
	2014		0.101	0.012	0.089	1.03	overvalued
	2015		0.122	0.103	0.019	1.02	overvalued
	2016		0.117	0.104	0.013	0.41	overvalued

Above mention table no. 10.0 depicts under / Overvaluation of companies during the study period. For that purpose researcher calculate Expected Return as per CAPM approach. Actual return can be calculated by simple return formula, for that purpose day to day share price has been collected from the official website of BSE. Furthermore researcher has been attempting to discover whether securities are undervalued or overvalued. Practical real-world purposes an asset's given price is compared or expected

return relative to what it should be according to the CAPM, and in that context, over/ under pricing is discussed.

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

Author has found that traditional performance evaluation tool i.e. adjusted net operating profit shows healthy financial position of the company. Furthermore it was also analyze that EVA is one of the most important performance evaluation tool which shows true and fair financial position of the business unit. It was also found that there is no significant difference in the value creation ability during the study period. ANOVA for EVA during the study period based on that it was found that null hypothesis has been rejected for value creation ability for sampled companies. It shows that there is a significant difference in the value creation ability of sampled companies. Furthermore study has also concluded that null hypothesis has been accepted for value creation ability during the study period. It shows that there is no significant difference in the value creation ability during the study period. Author has suggested that Investors should take their investment decision based on EVA statement of the companies, actual return of the company, risk factor of the company etc.

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